

Supporting Information

Self-Templating Construction of 3D Hierarchical Macro-/Mesoporous Silicon from 0D Silica Nanoparticles

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Figure S1. N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherms (a) and the corresponding BJH pore size distribution curve (b) of the commercial nano-sized silicon.

Figure S2. N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherms (a) and the corresponding BJH pore size distribution curve (b) of the "HCl-washing" silicon.

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammetry (a, c, and e) and galvanostatic discharge/charge profiles (b, d, and f) of the “HCl-washing” silicon (a, b), commercial nano-sized silicon (c, d) and commercial μm-sized silicon (e, f).

Figure S4. Cycling performance of the "HCl-washing" silicon.

Figure S5. Rate performance of the "HCl-washing" silicon.

Figure S6. UV-Vis spectra of the “HF-etching” silicon, commercial nano-sized silicon and μm -sized silicon.

Figure S7. Galvanostatic discharge/charge curves from 0.005 V to 2.7 V at the current density of 0.1 A g^{-1} .